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Effect Of Demonstration And Discussion Method Of Teaching On Students' Academic Performance In Public Secondary Schools In Jakusko Local Government Area Of Yobe State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of teaching methods on students' academic performance of in public secondary schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe State. The study was anchored on Thorndike view of modern learning and conditioning experiment. The researchers used survey research design for study while the simple random sampling technique was utilized to determine the sample for the study. A sample of 115 respondents was used and primary information was obtained by the use of a structured questionnaire from four selected secondary schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe State. The data collected were analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. The probability value of the regression estimate was used in testing the hypotheses of the study. The result of the regression analysis indicates that both Demonstration and Discussion Method has positive effect on students' academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe State, Nigeria and the relationship is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The relationship is in line with a priori expectation. It was concluded that demonstration and discussion methods promote learners' participation and build the required level of reasoning among students. It was recommended that Curriculum planners should incorporate guidelines that encourage participatory learning approaches like demonstration and discussion methods of teaching.

Keywords: Teaching method, demonstration method, discussion Method and Academic Performance

Introduction

The effect of teaching methods on students' learning should be the interest of every teacher and student. In the field of education, there have been various studies done in an attempt to measure teaching methods. Robinson and colleagues (1990) conducted a case study on several teaching methods in schools to explore

the reasons for their use, and perceptions of effectiveness. The result of their study suggested that various methods do influence teaching effectiveness.

In recent times, much research attention has been focused on teaching of Nigerian Secondary Schools with a view to ascertaining the adequacy and appropriateness of the teachers' method of teaching and indeed the effectiveness of instruction. Investigation into the use of demonstration instructional technique in the teaching in Nigerian Secondary Schools seem to have focused mainly on teachers' frequency of the use of this technique and sparingly on the application of important variables influencing its effective use. In a sense, no research attention has yet been paid to the effectiveness of teaching using demonstration technique. The use of demonstration instructional technique as an innovative instructional practice can only be effectively implemented if the teachers possess the appropriate knowledge, skills and abilities related to its use in the classroom situation. Skills for the demonstration technique consist of the teachers' awareness and understanding of the issues surrounding demonstration teaching. These include knowledge of questioning, identification of events that are suited to demonstration. Others are how to demonstrate curiosity and independent thoughts in students (Brown, 1999). They also include ability to elicit students' questions (Kona, 2000)

The discussion method has been widely accepted and recommended by some educators as the good method of teaching in secondary schools (Phipps & Osborne, 1988). The discussion method is the method of teaching where the central and essential characteristic is interaction (Binkley and Tulloch, 1981). During discussion session students participate in the learning process by contributing problems, analyzing the factors associated with the problems, developing possible solutions to the problems, placing the solution(s) into action, and evaluating the results of the solution.

This paper attempts to examine the demonstration and discussion method of teaching, and empirically establish its effect on Junior Secondary Schools academic performance in Jakusko local Government area in Yobe state.

Statement of the Problem

The poor academic performance by majority of the students in various subject areas is basically linked to the application of ineffective teaching methods by teachers to impact knowledge to learners and therefore teachers need to be conversant with numerous teaching strategies (Adunola, 2011). Teaching a subject has drawn a lot of controversy on the appropriate methods to be applied for student's better understanding. Yet no clear method can be plainly pointed as the most appropriate since there is a decline in academic performance in public secondary schools in the study area. Hence the study investigated how demonstration and discussion methods of teaching affect students' academic performance in public junior secondary schools in Jakusko LGA in Yobe state

Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

- i. Investigate the effect of demonstrative method on students' academic performance in public junior Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe state, Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the effect of discussion method on students' academic performance in public junior Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe state, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated in order to obtain answer to the problems under investigation:

- i. What is the effect of demonstrative method students' academic performance in public junior Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe state, Nigeria?
- ii. What effect does discussion method have on students' academic in public junior Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe state, Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

- i. **H₀₁**: Demonstration method has no significant effect on students' academic performance in public junior Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe state, Nigeria.
- ii. **H₀₂**: Discussion method has no significant effect on students' academic performance in public junior Secondary Schools in Jakusko Local Government Area in Yobe state, Nigeria s

Conceptual Clarifications

Teaching Method

Teaching method is a teaching device or strategy adopted by a teacher to teach a lesson and this includes the use of games, text books etc. that stimulates learning. Teaching methods are often divided into two broad categories: teacher-centred methods (also called direct instruction) and learner-centred methods (also called indirect instruction or inquiry-based learning) (Adamu 2020). Demonstration and discussion are also some of the methods used by some instructors in classroom situation. Demonstration method is the type of teaching method in which the teacher is the principal actor while the learners watch with the intention to act later. Discussion Method on the other hand is an interactive teaching strategy that encourages dialogue, participation, and collaborative learning among students and between students and the teacher.

Theoretical framework

The study is based on the Thorndike view of modern learning and conditioning experiment. This law put emphasis on the importance of this practice and its importance in the learning process, reward and get more improvement in performance. Continuous practice/repeating the task helps in binding response together (conditioned response). Thorndike theory also help to guide the researcher to establish whether to use or disuse of rewards have any effect on academic performance in teaching as subjects. It helps to establish if attitude towards a subjects and teaching methods affects students' academic performance.

Review of Empirical studies

Duruji, Azuh, Segun, Olanrewaju and Okorie (2014) examined teaching method and assimilation of students in tertiary institutions: a study of covenant university, Nigeria. The choice of teaching method which is the general principles, pedagogy and management strategies used for classroom instruction is very important to a degree of assimilation by the recipient of teaching. Teaching theories primarily fall into two categories or "approaches"; teacher-centered and student-centered. In the former, teachers are the main authority figure in this model. Students are viewed as empty vessels whose primary role is to passively receive information (via lectures and direct instruction) with an end goal of testing and assessment. However in a student-centered approach, teachers and students play an equally active role in the learning process. The teacher's primary role is to coach and facilitate student learning and overall comprehension of material. Student learning is measured through both formal and informal forms of assessment, including group projects, student portfolios, and class participation. The main aim of this paper is to examine the relationship between teaching method and assimilation of students and the impact on examination performance. A sample of 300 students cutting across the various schools and colleges in Covenant University who have taken at least not less than two semesters examinations was used for the study. Student-Lecturer relationship, examination contents, students' mode of study and assimilation, effort and students' CGPA were the parameters used for this purpose and it was found that assimilation is better with student-centered approach.

Daluba (2013) investigated the effect of demonstration method of teaching on students' achievement in agricultural science in secondary school in Kogi East Education Zone of Kogi State. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The study employed a quasi-experimental research design. Research questions and the hypothesis were answered using mean, standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The result of study revealed that demonstration method had significant effect on students' achievement than those taught with the conventional lecture method.

Das and Karuna (2005) examined Secondary School Education in Assam (India) with Special Reference to Mathematics. The paper describes the prevailing academic scenarios of a representative group of secondary schools in Assam (India) with special references to students' performance in general and mathematics performance in particular. The state of Assam is one of the economically backward regions of India and is witnessing socio-political disturbances mainly centered with younger population. Object oriented education leading ensured employment is expected to reduce the present social crisis in this region. Appropriate secondary school knowledge backed by perfect learning in mathematics can make students competent for future career. Investigation of prevailing education scenario vis-à-vis mathematics

performance of students of 21 representative schools of Assam revealed wide variations of academic environment amongst the school so also the variations of performances. The financial and managerial statuses of the schools seem to be major factors influencing academic performance. In general, academic performances as well as mathematics performances of the government and private schools are better than the schools not getting government aids. The study also revealed that mathematics performances of schools are positively correlated with (a) the academic performance of school indicated by school leaving pass percentage and also (b) with the performances in subjects other than mathematics. On the other hand, students and teacher ratio seems not to affect the mathematics performance of the schools. Improvement of the performance of secondary school in Assam is required considering the societal needs.

Uche and Chinyere (2011) studied Poor Performance of Nigerian Students in Mathematics in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE): What Is Not Working? This paper considered the importance of mathematics to the individual as well as to the nation. It noted that students' performance in this all important subject has been dismal especially in the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). The poor performance trend is indeed worrisome as seen from the summary of students' result in SSCE mathematics covering many years in the study. This is despite various efforts by government and its agencies, private organizations and other stakeholders in the education business to boost achievement of students in the subject. It becomes, therefore, a clear indication that certain things have still not been put in place. The paper considered these problems yet unsolved and recommended among others that efforts made at carrying out researches should not be allowed to waste away. Research results should be made to reach the implementers of the findings to be able to achieve the desired result.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. This design is appropriate because it allows the researcher to collect data from a large number of respondents at a particular time with the aim of describing existing conditions, practices, or opinions (Creswell & Creswell, 2018)

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all junior secondary school students (334) and teachers (54) in the four selected junior secondary schools in **Jakusko** Local Government Area. The choice of both teachers and students was based on the assumption that both groups are directly involved in the teaching-learning process and can provide valid data about the effectiveness of teaching methods.

Table 1: Number of students in the selected schools

Sn	Name of school	School population
1	GDJSS Jakusko	123
2	GDJSS Gwayo	53
3	GDJSS Karage	61
4	GDJSS Dachia	97
Total		334

Source: Author's Computation, 2026

Table 2: Number of Teachers in the selected schools

Sn	Name of school	Sample population
1	GDJSS Jakusko	16
2	GDJSS Gwayo	11
3	GDJSS Karage	13
4	GDJSS Dachia	14
Total		54

Source: School record, 2026

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample size was drawn from the population to make the study manageable. Within each selected school, a simple random sampling was used to select students. The sample size includes sample of 15 teachers and

sample of 100 students from the four selected secondary schools, which is considered adequate for meaningful statistical analysis.

Research Instrument

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire contained both closed-ended items based on a five-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, Strongly Disagree) and open-ended items that allowed respondents to express additional views.

Validity of the Instrument

To ensure content validity, the draft questionnaire was reviewed by two experts: two lecturers in Educational Measurement and Evaluation at Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashua. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated before the final copy of the questionnaire was produced.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the questionnaire was determined through a pilot test conducted in a secondary school outside the study area. The responses were subjected to a Cronbach’s Alpha reliability test, which produced a coefficient of 0.82, indicating high internal consistency and reliability of the instrument.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the selected teachers and students with the help of two trained research assistants. Respondents were assured of confidentiality and that their responses would be used strictly for academic purposes. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately to ensure a high return rate.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were coded and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency counts and percentages were used to summarize demographic data, while mean and standard deviation were used to analyze responses to the research questions. Since the instrument was based on a Likert scale, a cut-off mean score of **3.0** was used as the benchmark for decision-making. Data analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to ensure accuracy and reliability of results.

Model Specification

Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the effect or outcome of the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables of the study. The traditional multiple regression formula and its implicit forms are represented below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + e$$

Where, Y = Student's Performance, X_1 = Demonstration Method; X_2 = Discussion Method,

A priori expectations: The priori expectations is that β_1 and β_2 are positive

Data Analysis Techniques

Various statistical methods were used in analyzing this study: percentages, frequency and tables were used to examine the respondents’ bio-data. Multiple Regressions was used to assess the nature and degree of relationship between the students’ academic performance and teaching methods (Demonstration Method and Discussion Method)

Decision rule: The following decision rules were adopted for accepting or rejecting hypotheses: If the probability value ($p > 0.05$) we accept the null hypothesis, that is, we accept that the at the 5% level of significance. If the If the probability value ($p < \text{critical value}$) we reject the null hypothesis, in other words, that is, we accept that the estimate is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION

Table 3: Perception of Demonstration Method

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
Demonstration method helps in covering syllabus on time	52	30	10	8	3.26
Enhances theoretical understanding	48	30	14	8	3.18
Encourages passive learning	44	32	16	8	3.12
Discourages creativity and interaction	30	38	20	12	2.86
Reduces student engagement in class	26	42	20	12	2.82
Average Mean Score:					3.05

Source: Author’s Computation 2026

Interpretation: The demonstration method is effective, with strength in delivering both theoretical and practical content and is favorable for student engagement and creativity.

Table 4: Perception of Discussion Method

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
Promotes student interaction and participation	60	30	6	4	3.46
Improves understanding and retention of knowledge	50	36	10	4	3.32
Increases motivation and interest in learning	55	28	12	5	3.33
Encourages critical thinking and communication	52	30	10	8	3.26
Enhances practical understanding and teamwork	48	34	12	6	3.24
Average Mean Score:					3.32

Sources: Author’s Computation 2026

Interpretation: The discussion method is highly effective across all variables, especially in promoting engagement, motivation, and deep understanding.

Table 5: Path Coefficient

Hypotheses	Beta Value	Std. Error	T Stat	P Value	Decision
H ₀₁ : DEM->PERM	0.55	0.01	14.86	*** 0.05	Rejected
H ₀₂ : DIS->PERM	0.12	0.03	2.72	***0.05	Rejected

Source: Field Survey, (2026)

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: There is significant relationship between discussion method and students’ academic performance. The data obtained in Table 5 revealed that there was a positive significant relationship between discussion method and students’ academic performance (It is significant at P value <.01.). The null hypothesis is therefore is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between demonstration method and students’ academic performance.

Hypothesis two: The regression analysis was also found to be significant at P value <.03. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between discussion method and students’ academic performance was therefore rejected.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

From the findings, it was revealed that a significant relationship exist between demonstration method and students’ academic performance (P value <.01.). This finding is in line with that of Daluba (2013) who investigated the effect of demonstration method of teaching on students’ achievement in agricultural science in secondary school in Kogi East Education Zone of Kogi State and found that demonstration method had significant effect on students’ achievement than those taught with the conventional lecture method. This is also line with Mundi (2006) that opined that demonstration teaching method is advantageous in the following ways: it saves time and facilitates material economy; is an attention inducer and a powerful motivator in lesson delivery; students receive feedback immediately through their own products; it gives a real-life situation of course of study as students acquire skills in real-life situations using tools and materials; it help to motivate students when carried out by skilled teachers and it is good in showing the appropriate ways of doing things.

In addition, the findings show that a significant relationship exist between discussion method and students’ academic performance ((P value <.03). This result is in agreement with Wiggins (1987) who reported that interaction between the teacher and students during the teaching and learning process encourages the students to search for knowledge rather than the lecturer/teacher monopolizing the transmission of information to learners. This shows that there was a significant relationship between both method and students’ academic performance.

CONCLUSION

We can conclude discussion and demonstration methods help teachers plan more, talk less and students learn more while interacting with groups. The result also proves that, demonstration and discussion methods promote learners' participation and build the required level of reasoning among students. Demonstrations and discussions methods have been found to have a statistically positive effect on the performance of students in the study area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Curriculum planners should incorporate guidelines that encourage participatory learning approaches like demonstration and discussion methods of teaching.
1. Classroom sizes should be managed to make the discussion method more feasible and effective by allowing all students to participate actively.

Recommendations for Further Studies

A similar study should be conducted at the tertiary education level to compare demonstration methods and discussion methods in the tertiary institutions.

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